

THE ROLE OF TORCH INFECTION IN EARLY MISCARRIAGE. MORPHOLOGICAL STUDY**Teacă Irina,***Student, Faculty of General Medicine, State University of Medicine and Pharmacy
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Background: Early miscarriage is the spontaneous loss of intrauterine pregnancy before 12 weeks of gestation. Spontaneous abortion is a frequent complication of pregnancy that represents approximately 10% of pregnancy pathologies and 80% of all abortions. The most susceptible period in pregnancy for early abortion is in the first 10 weeks of gestation when organogenesis takes place. The study of the clinical-morphological peculiarities in spontaneous abortion causes changes in the chorio-villus profile and the gestational vascular remodelling with the development of primary placental insufficiency. TORCH infections are a major source of pregnancy disruption at early gestational age.

Conclusions: Placental components, particularly the syncytiotrophoblast (SYN), represent an important protective barrier in the transmission of transplacental infections. TORCH infection, during the gestation period, causes disturbances in the early development of the placenta with the involvement of the vascular component and the villous profile with a negative impact on the pregnancy resulting in miscarriage. The evaluation of the morphopathological profile during the early development period of the embryo-feto-placental complex will provide information regarding the characteristic changes induced by infections in the context of the abortive disease.

Keywords: Early miscarriage, chorionic villi, placenta, vascular component, TORCH infection.

Introduction

Early miscarriage is the spontaneous loss of intrauterine pregnancy before 12 weeks of gestation [15]. Although it is common [15], miscarriage is less studied, in approximately 50% of cases the aetiology is unknown, and in 50% it is multifactorial [30]. In humans, the placenta forms a protective barrier for the embryo that restricts the hematogenous spread of microorganisms [3]. In general, congenital infections associated with miscarriage, are a major cause of mortality and morbidity worldwide. In order to establish the diagnosis of early miscarriage, an important role is attributed to the morphological examination. Ultimately, the morphological examination of the placenta will identify pathological changes with disease in the villous tree and the remodelling of the spiral arteries induced by the infectious disturbances. The human placenta controls the infections by inducing a unique immunomodulatory response.

The SYN have a direct role in the protection of the embryo from infections. The continuous multinucleated cell layer of syncytiotrophoblast (SYN) is resistant and destroys hematogenous microorganisms by restrict parasite attachment, inhibiting invasion and active intracellular replication [3]. TORCH infection is a congenital group of microbial infection with vertical transmission. Infectious agents included in TORCH infection are *Toxoplasma gondii* (T), Others (O) such as *Listeria monocytogenes*, *Troponema pallidum*, Parvovirus, HIV, etc., Rubella (R), cytomegalovirus (C), and Herpesvirus (H) [5]. The morpho-pathological study will evaluate the morphological structure of the utero-placental complex complicated with early spontaneous abortion with an infectious substrate and will establish

the morpho-pathological criteria in primary placental insufficiency.

Histological profile in gravidar endometrium.

To ensure the implantation of semi-allogenic blastocyst, the endometrium will undergo a complex of functional and structural changes determined by progesterone, necessary for adaptations to the blastocyst during pregnancy. Progesterone is secreted by the corpus luteum and will maintain the secretory phase of the endometrial glands [20]. The endometrium will go through the cell differentiation phase with endometrial pre-decidualization [20], then complete decidualization specialized for blastocyst implantation with typical signs in the morphological picture. So, the high level of progesterone transforms the mucosa uterine into the decidua basalis. The hallmark of decidua gravidaris is secretory decidual glands and abundant vascularity [10]. Glands become hypersecretory, known as the Arias-Stella reaction [37]. The secretory glands are enlarged [27], spiral in appearance, and rich in glycogen, immunosuppressants, glycodepin A, and uteroferrin, necessary for the histiotrophic nutrition of the postimplantation trophoblast [10, 16].

The early period of placentation

In the fertilization process, in the fallopian tubes, daily the zygote goes through the segmentation stage, dividing into a blastomere, then a morula, and later a blastocyst that will migrate into the uterus and attach to the endometrial mucosa [32]. The decidua basalis have a critical role in the homeostatic balance between the mother and foetus. In the process of pregnancy, the decidua basalis includes genetic predisposition and immunological balance that ensures a strong immunological tolerance function for the protection, attachment

and invasion of the trophoblast perceived as a semi-allograft by the maternal immune system [24] and allows the attachment and implantation of the blastocyst [5]. The maternal-fetal interface has multiple immune cells vitals for the developing foetus [10]. Therefore, the decidua contains 40% immune cells, of which 70% are uterine natural killers (NKu), 25% - are macrophages and 3-5% T cells [5]. Natural killer cells are essential for embryo nutrition and vessel remodelling [10]. After attachment, the blastocyst separates into 2 layers: external-embryoblast and internal trophoblast [37]. With implantation, the trophoblast passes through the pre-lacunar stage with the division into 2 columns syncytiotrophoblast (SYN) and cytotrophoblast (CTB) [22]. Later, in the syncytiotrophoblast, appear trophoblastic lacunae filled with maternal blood that divide into trabeculae, characteristic changes for the lacunar stage [37]. The SYN also erodes into decidual glands and trophoblast is completely embedded in the decidua and obtains the histiotrophic nutrition necessary for the development [22]. The cytotrophoblast, with synthesis from the primary chorionic plate, invades the lacunar trabeculae and forms the primary villi [21]. Extraembryonic mesenchyme penetrate through the primary villi core and starts the development of the secondary villi [21]. Later, around day 18, the cytotrophoblast invades the maternal tissues and the spiral arteries, thus establishing the fetoplacental circulation in which the embryo will obtain chemotrophic nutrition having direct access to the maternal blood [21]. Thus, on day 18-20 p.c, the first fetal capillaries are identified in the chorionic villi and the primary vascular network is formed, and the secondary villi with vascular proliferation processes become tertiary villi [21]. Next, is the arrangement of the villous tree in cotyledons and the expansion of the fetoplacental circulation throughout the villous mass [21]. Until the end of gestation, the uteroplacental complex is irrigated by 2 vascular systems. The open circulatory system with the origin of the spiral arteries (uteroplacental and intervillous) and the embryo-fetal vascular system of the closed type consists of 2 arteries and an umbilical vein [21].

The role of the syncytiotrophoblast in limiting infection

The first barrier to infectious agents in maternal blood is the syncytiotrophoblast. The syncytiotrophoblast represents a continuous multinucleated layer of cells involved in the protection of the product of conception against infection [15]. Accordingly, damage to SYN destroys the passage of the pathogen to the chorionic villus, because CTB is permissive to infection [18]. The SYN have a direct role in the protection of the embryo from infections. The syncytio has lytic action at the level of attachment, invasion and intracellular replication of microorganisms [15]. Because anchoring villi are not delimited by SYN and villous capillaries are in direct contact with maternal blood, terminal villi will be considered weakly permissive sites for microorganisms [18]. A morphological marker characteristic of the passage of the placental barrier with the microorganisms is the inflammatory response

perivascular and in the villi with accumulation of immunocompetent cells (macrophages, lymphocytes, plasma cell and granulocytes) [18].

Toxoplasma gondii

T. gondii is a protozoan parasite with strictly intracellular replication [13]. The infection is transmitted by the sick cat excreting the oocyst [11, 14]. These oocysts once passed out from cat through feces, can contaminate the soil, water or vegetables and fruits which are consumed by pregnant women without washing. It is known that 30% of the global population presents an asymptomatic form with chronic *T. gondii* infection, with exacerbation in an immunosuppressed state [19]. Vertical transmission of the parasite from mother to embryo occurs [35] in approximately 50% of cases. A major risk of spontaneous abortion is presented by women primarily infected during pregnancy [32] when antibodies to *T. gondii* are missing. At the morphological investigation stage, free tachyzoites and tissue pseudocysts can be identified in the toxoplasmosis placenta [35]. Pseudocysts causing reduced inflammation and can be visualized by HE and PAS staining. Endozoites condition active inflammation and are identified by Giemsa staining [35]. The immunological response in the presence of a recent infection is the hyperproduction of Ig M, followed by Ig G [31, 33]. Susceptible to infection are anchoring villi and CTB [32]. Inhibition of parasite replication at the placental level is achieved by macrophages activated by IFN- γ [29]. The characteristic histological features of the infection are the delayed maturation of the villi with an intense degree of proliferation of Hofbauer macrophages, a reduced degree of placental vs embryonic inflammation and lymphohistiocytic reaction [29]. Typical for placental toxoplasmosis is characteristic villitis with villous conglutination and numerous cysts around the umbilical vein [32]. At the same time, the vascular component is also affected by the formation of thrombi in the chorionic vessels and the calcification of the arterial walls [32]. Under the globally aggravating statistics and the severity of the pathology, routine investigation of women planning a pregnancy is recommended. At the same time, in the prevention of this infection, it is necessary to take into account the way how the meat is prepared, avoiding the consumption of partially prepared meat. Pregnant women should refrain from contact with street cats, and if they live in the same house with their cat, it will be recommended to take care of it with gloves. Cat faeces will be collected at least 24 h after defecation [31].

Syphilis (Troponema pallidum)

Approximately 2 million pregnant women have been diagnosed with syphilis annually [25]. *Troponema pallidum* is a gram-negative spirochete that represents the infectious agent in syphilitic infection [7]. Transplacental infection can cause congenital infection with varied degree of clinical manifestations [31, 32]. The symptoms of *T. pallidum* infection in pregnant women appear in three stages. Initially, are affected the lymphatic system (lymphadenitis) and the skin with lesions on the skin where the bacteria entered the body called a chancre. Secondary syphilis appears a few weeks after the chancre has healed, and the pregnant

woman complains of irritation and rashes on the hands and feet. Symptoms persist for several weeks and disappear forever or may recur in a situation of immunosuppression. 15-30% of pregnant women may present symptoms with neurological, cardiovascular and osteo-articular damage, characteristic for tertiary stage of syphilis [31]. Congenital syphilis is transmitted from the fetus in the first and second stages [25]. The macroscopic examination reveals a voluminous and pale placenta, specific for fetal anaemia [32]. At the villous level, is determined the microscopic triad: increased villi, stromal hypercellularity and villous immaturity vs gestational age [25]. Occasionally, can be determined acute lymphohistiocytic villitis or peritonitis occurs with a predominance of CD3 lymphocytes and plasma cells, and the immunohistochemical test identifies few inclusions with spirochetes [6, 34]. Sensitive to pathological changes are the growth buds of the villous tree, where is determined hyperplasia of stromal cells, with pronounced edema of fetal capillaries and endo- vs perivascular fibrous tissue deposition with the development of venous and arterial vascular insufficiency, resulting in fetal malperfusion followed by embryonic death [32].

Parvovirus B19

It is a DNA virus [31] that occurs with a frequency of 1-400 pregnancies, in most cases manifesting itself asymptotically [15, 32]. Statistically, the risk for early spontaneous abortion is registered starting from weeks 4-6 of gestation [32, 26]. For routine diagnosis of "erythema infectiosum," it is used immunohistochemical examination which confirms the presence of NCL-PARVO antibodies [15]. The hallmark of infection with parvovirus B19 is hyperchromatosis of nuclei in giant cells with granulocyte necrosis [32]. Sometimes vascular damage can be observed with the presence of lymphocytic inflammation in the endothelium of the umbilical artery [32]. Many times, can be determined trophoblast apoptosis and calcifications in the stroma of the villi with marginal oedema [32]. In the fetus, it causes severe anaemia and pronounced hydrops with the presence of erythroid inclusions that require PCR confirmation [28].

RUBELLA

Global vaccination has greatly reduced the incidence of rubella infection during pregnancy [32]. Infection with the rubella virus, during early gestation, causes pathological changes at the level of the fetoplacental complex with evolution in spontaneous abortion [23]. A wide area of villi is usually affected with necrosis, fibrosis and stromal sclerosis and obliteration of spiral artery branches [23, 32]. Fetal malperfusion is the result of the activation of both villous and perivascular inflammatory mechanisms with the involvement of Hofnauer macrophages and intervillous and perivascular eosinophilic inclusions [32].

To prevent rubella infection, the MMR (measles, rubella, mumps) vaccination is recommended for women one month before conception [21, 32].

Cytomegalovirus (CMV)

Infection (CMV) affects 1% of pregnant women [32] and is transmitted to the fetus in approximately

40% of cases [32]. CMV is a member of the virus family, Betaherpesviridae, with a DNA genome [31]. It has been shown that infection in early gestation is much more severe than infection in late gestation [32].

Microscopically, through the PCR reaction, viral inclusions are identified at the decidua level, villous cytotrophoblast, anchoring villi and extravillous trophoblast [36]. Often spontaneous abortion occurs following the development of hydrops in the embryo [32] and is correlated with the severity of the infection. In the villous we can see tissue necrosis and inflammatory process that cause lymphohistiocytic villitis with eosinophilic and viral inclusion, lymphocytic infiltrates in the nucleus and cytoplasm and large Hofbauer cells [36]. Consistent with this, in the embryonic vascular system, we identify avascular regions with pronounced vascular involution and severe hypoxia [38]. Often the endo- and perivascular edema of the chorionic vessels causes vascular obstructions due to thrombosis and calcifications. A distinct sign of Cytomegalic aggression is the finding of "owl eyes" in the Chorio-villous compartment [32].

Herpes simplex virus (HSV)

It belongs to the herpesviridae family and has two forms HSV 1 and HSV 2 [30]. Infection HSV is considered one of the most aggressive viral infections resulting in spontaneous abortion if the pregnant women are infected in the early term of gestation [31]. It is transmitted vertically through the entry mediators HveA, HveB, and HveC present in the cytotrophoblast [18]. HSV pathogens utilise the fetomaternal interface as a replication surface before diffusion to the placenta and fetal compartment. Viral invasion causes non-specific HSV histopathological manifestations, therefore often any inflammatory response at the level of the fetoplacental complex requires the performance of diagnostic tests for HSV [9]. Herpetic placentitis is characterized by an acute lymphocytic villitis in early diagnosis and chronic plasmacytic villitis with Cowdry A and Cowdry B inclusions in the extravillous trophoblast (EVT) and less in the villous trophoblast [18] in chronic infection. Also, HSV infection determine the villous necrosis and the immaturity of the villi which are often sclerosed with chronic intervillous manifested by abnormal deposits of fibrinoid in the intervillous space [9]. In severe forms, the vascular profile is affected by the deposit of fibrin, fetal lymphocytes and endovascular eosinophils with the development of the villous hypo/avascular network or the formation of vascular thrombi following inflammatory mechanisms [9, 12].

Conclusion

In this narrative review of specialized literature, we aimed to highlight the importance of the histological examination in elucidating the pathogenesis of spontaneous abortion. The identification of placental lesions specific to TORCH infection presents both common changes (villitis, intervillous, damage to the vascular component) but also distinct changes such as the inclusions specific to each pathogen that will guide the diagnosis and subsequent management. Also, some infections such as HSV and CMV are initially asymptomatic and only early morphological diagnosis will provide

the opportunity to intervene immediately until irreversible complications develop in the intrauterine development of the embryo.

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